

LOCAL BUCKLING OF COMPOSITE BEAMS

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SUMMARY

In this paper first explicit expressions are presented for the calculation of the buckling loads of long, rectangular composite plates with orthotropic layup. In these expressions uniform, linearly varying and shear loads are taken into account, the edges can be constrained, while the constraint coefficients can be different at the two edges. These results are then applied for the local web buckling of composite beams. The results are verified numerically.

Keywords: buckling, local buckling, FRP, beam

INTRODUCTION

Local buckling analysis is a major consideration in the design of thin-walled FRP sections. Local buckling analyses of members can be performed by modeling the wall segments as orthotropic plates and by assuming that edges common to two or more plates remain straight. Then the buckling load is determined either (i) „exactly” (assuming that all the wall segments buckle simultaneously and the continuity conditions at the plate intersections are satisfied) or (ii) approximately, by considering the wall segments as individual plates, which are elastically restrained by the adjacent walls [1-8].

When the second method is used (e.g., only one of the wall segments is considered, which is elastically restrained by the adjacent walls) the two keys to the solution are (a) to determine the elastic restraints caused by the adjacent walls (see [1, 8]), and (b) to calculate the buckling load of the plate, whose edges are restrained.

Figure 1. Web with restrained edges. The restraining wall segment may have (a) two edges attached to adjacent walls or (b) one edge is free

Table 1. Buckling loads of long plates available in the literature

	Supports and loading	Buckling load	
1	 (Lekhnitskii [13])	$N_{x,cr} = \frac{\pi^2}{L_y^2} \left[2\sqrt{D_{11}D_{22}} + 2(D_{12} + 2D_{66}) \right]$	
2	 (Veres and Kollár [14])	$N_{x,cr} = \frac{\pi^2}{L_y^2} \left[3.125\sqrt{D_{11}D_{22}} + 2.33(D_{12} + 2D_{66}) \right]$	
3	 (Veres and Kollár [14])	$N_{x,cr} = \frac{\pi^2}{L_y^2} \left[4.53\sqrt{D_{11}D_{22}} + 2.44(D_{12} + 2D_{66}) \right]$	
4	 (Kollár and Springer [7])	$N_{x,cr} = \frac{\pi^2}{L_y^2} \left[2\sqrt{1 + 4.139\xi} \sqrt{D_{11}D_{22}} + (2 + 0.44\xi^2)(D_{12} + 2D_{66}) \right]$	
5	 (Lekhnitskii [13])	$N_{xb,cr} = \frac{\pi^2}{L_y^2} \left[13.4\sqrt{D_{11}D_{22}} + 10.4(D_{12} + 2D_{66}) \right]$	
6	 (Seydel [15])	$N_{xy,cr} = \frac{4}{L_y^2} \sqrt[4]{D_{11}D_{22}^3} (8.125 + 5.045K)$	$K \leq 1$
		$N_{xy,cr} = \frac{4}{L_y^2} \sqrt{D_{22}(D_{12} + 2D_{66})} \left(11.7 + \frac{1.46}{K^2} \right)$	$1 \leq K$
7	 (Seydel [15])	$N_{xy,cr} = \frac{4}{L_y^2} \sqrt[4]{D_{11}D_{22}^3} (15.07 + 7.08K)$	$K \leq 1$
		$N_{xy,cr} = \frac{4}{L_y^2} \sqrt{D_{22}(D_{12} + 2D_{66})} \left(18.59 + \frac{3.56}{K^2} \right)$	$1 \leq K$
8	 (Barbero [16])	$N_{x,cr} = 12 \frac{D_{66}}{L_y^2}$	
9	 (Kollár and Springer [7])	$N_{x,cr} = \frac{7}{\sqrt{1 + 4.12\xi}} \frac{\sqrt{D_{11}D_{22}}}{L_y^2} + 12 \frac{D_{66}}{L_y^2}$	
<p>$\xi = 1/(1+10\zeta)$ and $\zeta = D_{22}/(kL_y)$ for plates rotationally restrained by springs, $\xi = 1/(1+0.61\zeta^{1.2})$ and $\zeta = D_{22}L_y/GI_{12}$ for plates rotationally restrained by stiffeners, $K = (2D_{66} + D_{12})/\sqrt{D_{11}D_{22}}$.</p>			

We recall that depending on the configuration of the restraining wall, two kinds of restraining effects must be considered [8]. Either both edges are attached to adjacent walls or one of the long edges is free (Figure 1). In the first case the restraining effect is equivalent to that of rotational springs:

$$M_y = (\pm)k \frac{\partial w}{\partial y}, \quad (1)$$

while in the second case it is equivalent to the effect of a torsional stiffener [9]:

$$M_y = (\pm)GI_t \frac{\partial^3 w}{\partial x \partial y^2}, \quad (2)$$

Table 2. Buckling loads of long plates with identical restraining coefficients along the two edges. The expressions for cases 2 and 3 can also be applied when the tensile side is hinged or built-in. (ξ and K is given in Table 1.)

	Supports and loading	Buckling load	
1		$N_{x,b,cr} = \frac{\pi^2}{L_y^2} \left[26.8\sqrt{D_{11}D_{22}} + 12.9(D_{12} + 2D_{66}) \right]$	$K \leq 3$
		$N_{x,b,cr} = \frac{\pi^2}{L_y^2} \left[30.1\sqrt{D_{11}D_{22}} + 11.5(D_{12} + 2D_{66}) \right]$	$3 \leq K$
2		$N_{x,b,cr} = \frac{\pi^2}{L_y^2} \left[(13.4 + 13.4\xi)\sqrt{D_{11}D_{22}} + (10.4 + 2.5\xi^4)(D_{12} + 2D_{66}) \right]$	$K \leq 3$
		$N_{x,b,cr} = \frac{\pi^2}{L_y^2} \left[(13.4 + 16.7\xi^{1.4})\sqrt{D_{11}D_{22}} + (10.4 + 1.1\xi^\delta)(D_{12} + 2D_{66}) \right]$ $\delta = \min\{K, 8\}$	$3 \leq K$
3		$N_{x,b,cr} = \frac{\pi^2}{L_y^2} \left[13.4\sqrt{1 + 3\xi}\sqrt{D_{11}D_{22}} + (10.4 + 2.2\xi)(D_{12} + 2D_{66}) \right]$	$K \leq 3$
		$N_{x,b,cr} = \frac{\pi^2}{L_y^2} \left[13.4\sqrt{1 + 4.3\xi}\sqrt{D_{11}D_{22}} + (10.4 + 0.8\xi^2)(D_{12} + 2D_{66}) \right]$	$3 \leq K$
4		$N_{x,y,cr} = \frac{4}{L_y^2} \sqrt[4]{D_{11}D_{22}^3} \left(8.125\sqrt{1 + 2.44\xi} + (5.045 + 2.035\xi^2)K \right)$	$K \leq 1$
		$N_{x,y,cr} = \frac{4}{L_y^2} \sqrt{D_{22}(D_{12} + 2D_{66})} \left(11.71 + 6.88\xi + \frac{1.46 + 2.1\xi}{K^2} \right)$	$1 \leq K$
5		$N_{x,y,cr} = \frac{4}{L_y^2} \sqrt[4]{D_{11}D_{22}^3} \left(8.125\sqrt{1 + 2.44\xi} + (5.045 - 4.5\xi + 6.535\xi^2)K \right)$	$K \leq 1$
		$N_{x,y,cr} = \frac{4}{L_y^2} \sqrt{D_{22}(D_{12} + 2D_{66})} \left(\frac{11.71 + 1.18\xi + 5.7\xi^\delta}{1.46 + 2.1\xi^{4\delta}} \right)$ $\delta = \min\{K, 8\}$	$1 \leq K$

where k is the rotational spring stiffness, GI_t is the rotational stiffness of the stiffener (the calculations are given in [8]), M_y is the restraining moment, w is deflection, x and y are the longitudinal coordinate and the coordinate perpendicular to the long edges, respectively.

BUCKLING OF LONG PLATES WITH RESTRAINED EDGES

The buckling analyses of long orthotropic plates with different edge conditions were treated by several authors; however closed form expressions were available only for a few cases ([7, 10-12]). The results recommended by the authors are summarized in Table 1. (Note that further solutions are available in the literature, which can also be used [4-6, 12].) Only recently, explicit expressions were published for the calculation of the buckling loads of long plates subjected to *bending or shear* (Figure 2), when the

long edges are elastically restrained [17]. These cases are important for calculating the web buckling of beams subjected to bending or transverse loads, and hence are summarized in Table 2 and 3.

Figure 2. The considered plate (a) and its loads: uniform compression (b), linearly varying compression (i.e. bending) (c), shear (d)

Table 3. Buckling loads of long plates with different restraining coefficient along the two edges

	Load	Support	Buckling load	
1	axial	springs or stiffener	$N_{x,cr} = \frac{\pi^2}{L_y^2} \left[\left(2\sqrt{1 + \sqrt{2(\xi_1^2 + \xi_2^2 + 6\xi_1\xi_2)}} \right) \sqrt{D_{11}D_{22}} + \right. \\ \left. (2 + 0.22(\xi_1^2 + \xi_2^2))(D_{12} + 2D_{66}) \right]$	$K \leq 1$
			$\frac{\pi^2}{L_y^2} \left[\left(\sqrt{1 + 5.08\xi_1} + \sqrt{1 + 5.08\xi_2} \right) \sqrt{D_{11}D_{22}} + \right. \\ \left. (2 + 0.1(\xi_1^2 + \xi_2^2))(D_{12} + 2D_{66}) \right]$	$1 \leq K$
2	shear	springs	$\frac{4}{L_y^2} \sqrt[4]{D_{11}D_{22}^3} \left(4.06(\sqrt{1 + 2.44\xi_1} + \sqrt{1 + 2.44\xi_2}) + \right. \\ \left. (5.045 + 1.017(\xi_1^2 + \xi_2^2))K \right)$	$K \leq 1$
			$\frac{4}{L_y^2} \sqrt{D_{22}(D_{12} + 2D_{66})} \left(11.71 + 3.44(\xi_1 + \xi_2) + \frac{1.46 + 1.05(\xi_1 + \xi_2)}{K^2} \right)$	$1 \leq K$
3	shear	stiffener	$\frac{4}{L_y^2} \sqrt[4]{D_{11}D_{22}^3} \left(4.06(\sqrt{1 + 2.44\xi_1} + \sqrt{1 + 2.44\xi_2}) + \right. \\ \left. (5.045 - 2.25(\xi_1 + \xi_2) + 3.2675(\xi_1^2 + \xi_2^2))K \right)$	$K \leq 1$
			$\frac{4}{L_y^2} \sqrt{D_{22}(D_{12} + 2D_{66})} \left(\frac{11.71 + 0.59(\xi_1 + \xi_2) + 2.85(\xi_1^\delta + \xi_2^\delta)}{1.46 + 1.05(\xi_1^{4\delta} + \xi_2^{4\delta})} + \right. \\ \left. \frac{1.46 + 1.05(\xi_1^{4\delta} + \xi_2^{4\delta})}{K^2} \right)$	$1 \leq K$
			$\delta = \min\{K, 8\}$	
$\xi_{1,2} = 1/(1+10\zeta_{1,2})$ and $\zeta_{1,2} = D_{22}/(k_{1,2}L_y)$ for plates rotationally restrained by springs, $\xi_{1,2} = 1/(1+0.61(\zeta_{1,2})^{1.2})$ and $\zeta_{1,2} = D_{22}L_y/GI_{12}$ for plates rotationally restrained by stiffeners, $K = (2D_{66} + D_{12})/\sqrt{D_{11}D_{22}}$				

As a consequence, in the analysis of local buckling of FRP members [1] axial loads can be treated with sufficient accuracy, however the web buckling of transversely loaded beams could be approximated only by neglecting the restraining effects of the flanges [1]. In this paper the web buckling of transversely loaded beams will be discussed.

Interaction curve

When the axial load, the linearly varying load and the shear load act together Bleich [2] proposed interaction curves for the calculation of the buckling load: the plate buckles if the following equation holds:

$$\left(\frac{N_{xb}}{N_{xb,cr}}\right)^2 + \left(\frac{N_{xy}}{N_{xy,cr}}\right)^2 + \frac{N_x}{N_{x,cr}} = 1. \quad (3)$$

This expression was verified for simply supported and built-in isotropic plates. We made several comparisons for orthotropic plates with rotationally restrained edges and obtained that the accuracy of this approximation is about 7% and Eq.(3) is conservative[17].

PROBLEM STATEMENT

Thin-walled open or closed section beams are considered. The layup of each wall segment is orthotropic. The material and the layup may be different in each wall segment, but must be uniform within each wall segment of the member. External loads result in shear and linearly varying axial forces in the web (Figure 4). Our aim is to derive explicit expressions to determine the load on the member which results in local buckling.

Figure 4. Forces on the flange and on the web

APPROACH

For the web buckling of thin walled beams we will follow the steps given in [1 or 7]. They will be presented for a box beam and for an I beam (Figure 5) below, but can directly be applied also for C or Z section beams.

Step 1. Calculate the axial force, and shear force in the web and in the flanges.

When the loads of the beam are given – using the classical beam theory – the forces in the flanges and in the web(s) can be calculated. They are denoted by

$$(N_x)_f, (N_x)_w, (N_{xb})_w, (N_{xy})_w.$$

Subscripts f and w refer to the flange and to the web, respectively (Figure 5).

Step 2. Calculate the buckling load of the web and flanges assuming simply supported edges.

For the flange of the box beam or the I-beam the buckling loads are (see Case 1 and 8 of Table 1):

$$(N_{x,cr})_f^{ss} = \frac{\pi^2}{b_f^2} \left[2\sqrt{D_{11}^f D_{22}^f} + 2(D_{12}^f + 2D_{66}^f) \right] \quad (4)$$

$$\text{or } (N_{x,cr})_f^{ss} = \frac{12D_{66}^f}{(b_f/2)^2}. \quad (5)$$

Figure 5. Sizes of a box beam (a) and of an I-beam (b).

We define a critical load parameter λ_f^{ss} such that the load multiplied by λ_f^{ss} results in local buckling of the flange, assuming hinged supports: $\lambda_f^{ss}(N_x)_f = (N_{x,cr})_f^{ss}$. By rearranging this expression, we obtain:

$$\lambda_f^{ss} = \frac{(N_{x,cr})_f^{ss}}{(N_x)_f}. \quad (6)$$

The web may buckle under the combination of the axial, bending and shear force. When only one of these forces acts, its critical load can be calculated as (see Table 1 Case 1, 5 and 6 respectively)

$$(N_{x,cr})_w^{ss} = \frac{\pi^2}{b_w^2} \left[2\sqrt{D_{11}^w D_{22}^w} + 2(D_{12}^w + 2D_{66}^w) \right],$$

$$(N_{xb,cr})_w^{ss} = \frac{\pi^2}{b_w^2} \left[13.4\sqrt{D_{11}^w D_{22}^w} + 10.4(D_{12}^w + 2D_{66}^w) \right], \quad (7)$$

$$(N_{xy,cr})_w^{ss} = \frac{4}{b_w^2} \sqrt[4]{D_{11}^w (D_{22}^w)^3} (8.125 + 5.045K).$$

(The expressions are presented for the case of $K < 1$.) The critical load parameters for each force are calculated as:

$$\lambda_{x,w}^{ss} = \frac{(N_{x,cr})_w^{ss}}{(N_x)_w}, \quad \lambda_{b,w}^{ss} = \frac{(N_{xb,cr})_w^{ss}}{(N_{xb})_w}, \quad \lambda_{xy,w}^{ss} = \frac{(N_{xy,cr})_w^{ss}}{(N_{xy})_w}. \quad (8)$$

The load parameter of the web, λ_w^{ss} can be obtained from the interaction curve (Eq.3) as the root of the following equation:

$$\left(\lambda_w^{ss} \right)^2 \left(\left(\frac{(N_{xb})_w}{(N_{xb,cr})_w^{ss}} \right)^2 + \left(\frac{(N_{xy})_w}{(N_{xy,cr})_w^{ss}} \right)^2 \right) + \left(\lambda_w^{ss} \right) \left(\frac{(N_x)_w}{(N_{x,cr})_w^{ss}} \right) = 1. \quad (9)$$

Step 3. Check whether the web or the flange buckles first

If $\lambda_w^{ss} < \lambda_f^{ss}$ the web buckles first. We assume that this relationship holds. In case of $\lambda_f^{ss} < \lambda_w^{ss}$ the flange buckles first, and the steps given in [1, 5] should be followed.

Step 4. Calculate the k spring constant for a box beam or the torsional stiffness GI_t for an I beam. The restraining effects of the flanges of the box beam or of the I-beam are taken into account by the expressions [6]:

$$k_i = \frac{1}{r_i} k_o, \quad GI_{ti} = \frac{1}{r_i} GI_{to}, \quad i=1,2, \quad (10)$$

where $i=1,2$ refers to the top or to the bottom flange. k_o and GI_{to} are calculated as

$$k_o = \frac{2D_{22}^f}{b_f}, \quad GI_{to} = 4D_{66}^f b_f, \quad (11)$$

r_i takes into account the destabilizing effect of the compression load, with the factor [7]: $1/(1 - N/N_{cr})$. For the flange in compression it is calculated as

$$r_1 = \frac{1}{1 - \lambda_w^{ss} / \lambda_f^{ss}}. \quad (12)$$

The flange in tension is stabilized by the tensile stresses, this effect is neglected, and hence we assume that for the flange in tension $r_2 = 1$.

Step 5. Calculate the buckling load of the web assuming restrained edges. When the restraining effects are known, the buckling loads for each force can be calculated from the corresponding Cases of Tables 2 and 3 in [4], and the safety against buckling can be verified by Equation (9) in [4]. These calculations will be illustrated in the next section.

NUMERICAL EXAMPLES

To illustrate the usage and accuracy of the above method we present four numerical examples. In each case the critical load (which results in local buckling) of a single span, simply supported beam is presented. First, the loads are chosen such that they result in uniform bending and shear: the beam is subjected to concentrated end moments, to uniformly distributed moment, and to their combination. Finally a beam subjected to four point bending. We use an E-glass/vinylester box profile (Fig. 10), the material of which was also used by Bank ([1], p. 421). The geometrical and material properties are given in Table 5. and Fig. 10. and the material properties are $E_1 = 17.927$ GPa, $E_2 = 6.895$ GPa, $G_{12} = 12.93$ GPa, $\nu_{21} = 0.33$.

Figure 6. Numerical examples

Here only the results of the calculations are presented in Table 4, the details are given in [18].

Table 4. Load parameters due to local buckling

Case	Results obtained from the presented expressions	FE
Figure 6a	2.01	2.01
Figure 6b	1.53	1.54
Figure 6c	1.26	1.31
Figure 6d	1.26	1.62

The buckling shapes are given in Figures 7 and 8.

Note that in every case the presented expressions are on the safe side. The error is the highest in the last case when the bending moment and the shear force strongly varies at the critical cross section.

Figure 7. Buckling shape of the beam due to pure bending and shear (Figure 6a, b)

Figure 8. Buckling shape of the beam due to the combination of pure bending and shear; and due to four point bending (Figure 6c, d)

DISCUSSION

Approximate expressions are presented for the calculation of the buckling load of long orthotropic composite plates with restrained edges.

Using these expressions the local buckling analysis of thin walled composite beams given in the literature can be extended to all practical cases. In the derivation of the presented expressions several approximations were made:

- (1) Rather than considering an assembled section, we modeled the webs and flanges as individual orthotropic plates rotationally restrained at their edges.
- (2) In calculating the restraining effect we assumed cylindrical bending.
- (3) The stabilizing effect of tension was neglected.
- (4) We calculated the buckling loads of plates with rotationally restrained edges by approximate expressions.
- (5) The distribution of the shear along the web is assumed to be uniform, the shear in the flanges is neglected
- (6) The maximum values of the internal forces are taken into account, however, in most practical cases they vary along the length

Approximations (2), (3) and (6) are on the safe side, while approximations (4) may cause an error less than 7%. Note that approximation (6) may underestimate the buckling load by up to 10-20%.

Approximation (2) can be eliminated by taking into account the effect of the buckling length in the calculation of the spring constant, however it requires a rather complex calculation, and hence it is not recommended.

We emphasize that several comparisons were made with the results of finite element and analytical calculations, and we found the presented expressions to be reasonably accurate.

The analysis was developed for thin-walled members where the layup of each wall is symmetrical. For thin-walled members with unsymmetrical walls the presented formulas can be applied, as an approximation. In this case the reduced bending stiffnesses must be used [19]. The matrix of these reduced stiffnesses is calculated by Eq.(29) of [8].

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

This work was supported by the Hungarian Research Fund (OTKA- K 77803), which is highly appreciated.

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